

Obot, Abasiyanga-owo John; Prof. Enefiok Ibok & Dr. Sunday Ibanga

INTRA-COMMUNAL CONFLICTS AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN IKA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

¹OBOT, ABASIYANGA-OWO JOHN; ²PROF. ENEFIOK IBOK;

³DR. SUNDAY IBANGA

^{1,2&3}Department of Public Administration Faculty of Management Sciences

Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus

sabellaobot@gmail.com

Abstract

The meteoric rise in communal conflict in Nigeria has led to socio-economic degradation so much that warlords have exploited the situation for arbitrariness, thereby subjugating innocent citizens to underserved brutality. This research, therefore, aims at examining the effects of communal conflicts on socio-economic development using Ika Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, as a case study. To achieve this objective, social conflict theory and frustration aggression theory were adopted, two research questions and two corresponding hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The survey research design was adopted, and data were collected using a researcher-created questionnaire and analysed using the Pearson product moment correlation analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that communal conflicts significantly affect socio-economic development in the area of educational and agricultural development in Ika local government area, Akwa Ibom State. The study, therefore, recommended, among others, that the government should establish a policy that will eradicate and/or control communal conflicts in Ika local government area in Akwa Ibom State so as to instill peace in the affected sectors.

Keywords: Communal Conflict, Crises, Socio-economic Development, War, Education, Ika L.G.A

Introduction

1.1 Background to the study

Over the years, Nigeria as well as Akwa Ibom State have witnessed several communal conflicts. In spite of the level of social, political, and economic development, intra-communal or intra-ethnic feuds have become a social phenomenon in Nigeria, even in Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. From the earliest times, Nigerian

people have been neither incorrigibly insular nor irrationally impervious to external influences, nor have they been amateurishly unpractised in the art of neighbourliness. Even a casual perusal of the records would reveal in bold relief the judicious inclination of Nigerians to maintain harmonious relations with other people, especially those that they intermingle with for satisfaction or reciprocal needs.

Evidence indicates that Nigeria is a land of diversity, with people of different groups and communities with divergent norms, customs, values, taboos, ethnic, and political ideologies, which can periodically lead to frequent clashes resulting from economic, sociocultural, and political demands. As Ladi (2010) observes, "any nation that has conflict, unemployment, political instability, and security challenges cannot be said to be in the path of greatness and development because these divisive forces contribute greatly to the incidence of violent crimes such as murder, destruction of lives and property, mass killing, rape, arson, and even armed robbery. Naturally, conflicts within nation-states and in the international community are unavoidable; hence, the primary purpose of governments and international organisations like the United Nations is to settle disputes by peaceful means, in conformity with justice and international law, and to resolve international disputes and situations that might lead to breaches of peace. As evident in Articles 1(4) and 2(3) of the United Nations Charter, a specific obligation is provided for states not to use force in their interstate relations but to settle their disputes through peaceful means.

Communal conflict refers to situations involving people or social groups with different interests, mutually antagonistic tendencies, and opposing influences competing for the use of limited resources. Communal conflict can be implicit or explicit, proximate, local, regional, national, international, latent, or violent. Communal conflicts could result from tree crops, farmlands, wetlands, and water streams with overlapping combinations of porous boundaries and the management of common pool resources (Ramirez, 1999). According to Woolcock and Narayan (2002), communal conflict can be grouped into three broad categories: community-level conflict involving farmers within the same communities; intercommunity conflicts involving different communities or farmers from neighbouring villages; and super community conflicts involving farmers and communities with higher-level formal institutions.

The meteoric rise in communal conflict in Nigeria has led to economic degradation, so that warlords have exploited the situation for arbitrariness and subjugated innocent citizens to underserved brutality. However, it should be pointed out that everybody abhors conflict in whatever form, because the long run effects are that more people are thrown out of jobs, social amenities (both in rural and urban areas) are

destroyed, relationships amongst persons and groups are strained, and economic and other sundry activities are stalled. Thus, communal conflict is an outcome of a variety of factors, which create situations that promote crime. The widening gap between the rich and poor due to the impact of poverty, bad economic policies, corrupt political leaders and police officers, and welfare service disconnect cannot repress the rising trend in modern times that leads to violent crimes.

Conflict is both positive and negative. The aspect that represents genuine and articulated concern through dialogue and solutions that are preferred to alleviate a problem is termed positive conflict. While negative conflict is an index of social pathology reflected by social disorganisation in social values and unemployment that interrupt the harmony of society. Ayuk (2015) observes that, as the population of any community, state, nation, etc. increases and the need for land and other resources becomes more urgent, there will be intense competition to acquire access to and keep these resources. This can push people to secure what they have, which oftentimes involves violence and the eventual destruction of lives and property.

Like every human association, the people of Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State are not self-sufficient. As a result, they intermingle with one another in the course of their historical development. But sadly, the outbreak of communal conflicts in this local government area has resulted in serious negative effects. To authenticate this claim, Uya (2004) alluded to the fact that communal conflicts have brought harsh consequences on socio-economic development such as educational development, agricultural development, employee generation, and the growth of small and medium scale enterprises. As such, school activities were interrupted, farming activities were halted, and infrastructural facilities were destroyed, such as healthcare centres, markets, shops, houses, etc., thereby causing a high level of death amongst indigenes as well as devastating violence that has led to significant loss and decline in economic, social, and political activities in the local government area.

Violent intergroup conflicts in warring communities are detrimental to human life and property, disrupting socio-economic activities and development. It is crucial for responsible individuals in the Ika Local Government Area to implement peaceful ways of handling chieftaincy and political office sharing to accommodate other clans and promote peaceful living. Well-informed individuals with knowledge of their group history and social skills can resolve inter-ethnic tensions. To hold warring communities together, leadership members should be trained on managing inter-ethnic funds or conflicts. Non-governmental organisations, religious organisations, and philanthropic organisations provide such trainings. This study, therefore, seeks to examine communal

conflicts and socio-economic development in Ika Local Government Area warring communities' conflicts with a view to proffering solutions for lasting peace among the people of Ika Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Community members strive for peace, harmony, stability, equality, and socio-economic development. However, human co-existence often leads to disputes and differences, resulting in communal conflicts. These conflicts can have severe economic, political, and social effects. Intra-communal conflicts have been a recurring social phenomenon in Akwa Ibom State and, particularly, in Ika Local Government Area, thereby undermining the normal functioning of the community and its surroundings.

Ika Local Government Area since 1998 has been in communal conflicts because of the chieftaincy tussle and the sharing of political offices. Ika is a homogenous community with a common ancestry. It has its traditional headquarters in the Achan Ika Clan. Before the conflict, Ika people were known to have lived together in harmony and united in love. This age-long tradition of love, peace, and unity was broken by the intra-communal conflict, which was caused by political imbalance, village boundary issues, thuggery, and chieftaincy tussles.

These conflicts have impacted negatively on the land and other environmental resources, thereby reducing the socio-economic development potential of the natural resource base for the people. Thousands of residents were forced to flee the village, and rampaging mobs killed at will and set homes ablaze. The unbearable situation of the communal conflicts in Ika has abruptly affected educational development, economics, and agriculture development.

Despite the preponderance of conflict in rural communities and the institute for peace and conflict resolution to bring complete calmness and everlasting settlement, there is still some "silence war" among the communities and villages that were involved in the conflict. Also, there is still a knowledge gap regarding intra-communal conflicts and socio-economic development in the literature. Critical research has been carried out in this area. In an attempt to improve our understanding and fill this knowledge gap, the study will examine intra-communal conflicts and socio-economic development in Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

1.3 Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to examine the extent to which intra-communal conflicts affect socio-economic development in Ika Local Government Area. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- i. Investigate how intra-communal conflicts affect educational development in Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. Investigate how intra-communal conflicts affect agricultural development in Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

1.4 Research questions

To guide this study, the following research questions were raised:

- i. How do intra-communal conflicts affect educational development in Ika Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State?
- ii. To what extent do intra-communal conflicts affect agricultural development in Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State?

1.5 Research hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between communal conflicts and educational development in Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between communal conflicts and agricultural development in Ika Local Government Area conflict.

1.6 Significance of the study

The study will be of immense benefit to the warring communities, her citizens, and the Nigerian government, whose sole responsibility is to examine issues, legislate, and make policies that will address the incessant and intractable conflict amongst communities in Nigeria objectively.

Also, an area where conflicts persist will find this study beneficial. It will address the vexed questions of the people about the unlawful possession of arms to engage themselves in destructive conflict and criminal acts—a disagreement that would have been resolved amicably. Managers of conflict would equally benefit from this study with respect to proactive and preventive measures because the study spells out what will be done to forestall full-scale communal conflict with its accompanying negative consequences. On the other hand, the military and other security outfits will learn from the study, especially in mediating between or among conflicting communities.

Understanding the dangers inherent in participating in communal conflict is necessary for its control. Consequently, parents would benefit, as they would be better

informed to advise their children. Policymakers, administrators, and social scientists will find this study useful in their various capacities as they attempt to understand the dynamic nature of humans and finally reveal new frontiers for further research. Lastly, this research will not only contribute to the development of knowledge; it is a modest contribution to existing knowledge.

1.7 Limitation of the study

The study was limited by the information supplied by respondents on the effect of communal conflicts and socio-economic development. This was because Ika Local Government Area residents do not keep proper records of the effects of communal conflicts and socio-economic development. Thus, the researcher only relied on respondents' opinions and not on documentation. Furthermore, only one local government area was selected to represent all the warring local government areas in Akwa Ibom State. Thus, this does not really capture the general survey for the warring local government areas. Respondents were also afraid to give out information, but the researcher explained the objective of the research to them, so they were willing to fill out the questionnaire. Despite these limitations, the researcher was careful to use appropriate research design in the conduct of the present study. Thus, the findings of this study should be considered valid and useable regardless of the observed limitations.

Review of Relevant Literature and Theoretical Framework

2.1 Conceptual review

2.1 Conceptual Specification of Models

Source: Researcher's Conceptualization (2023)

The conceptual model shows the connection between the dependent variables and the independent variables for the study.

2.1.1 Conflict

Conflict has been conceptualised differently by several scholars based on their goals, interests, and aspirations. According to Rechler (2001), conflict is the pursuit of incompatible goals by different groups, or a linear phenomenon that consists of stages like initiation, escalation, maintenance, abatement, and termination. Conflict is an indispensable phenomenon in human social interactions. Thus, conflict is defined as a state or quality of ongoing relationships among social entities, such as persons, groups, or organisations. It results from a lack of agreement over an issue and is expressed in words and actions. Conflict is an escalated competition at any system level between groups whose aim is to gain an advantage over other groups.

Conflicts refer to disputes, disagreements, quarrels, struggles, fights, and wars between individuals, groups, and countries. In every nation, there is no complete agreement on how to share wealth, power, and status among individuals and groups and how to effect necessary changes and reforms. Since different groups and individuals have diverse interests, the aims of some groups will conflict with those of others. Conflicts occur when deprived groups and individuals attempt to increase their share of power and wealth or to modify the dominant values, norms, beliefs, or ideologies (Angaye, 2003).

According to Otite (2006), conflict is a disagreement between parties over limited resources, often involving verbal or physical attacks. It can lead to warfare or social disorganisation, necessitating conflict resolution or management. People often struggle with conflicts, but they are often motivated to manage them. Continuous encounters can cause societal disorganisation, hindering socio-economic and political development. Despite their inherent nature, individuals and societies are focused on resolving conflicts and normalizing social, interpersonal, and inter-group relations. Conflict and consensus are two sides of the same coin (Otite et al., 2006).

Pate (2009) noted that when two or more parties perceive their interests as incompatible, they express hostile attitudes or pursue their interests through actions that damage the other parties. In the view of Kari (2004), conflict arises when two actors are opposing each other in social interaction and reciprocal social power in an attempt to obtain scarce or incompatible goals by preventing each other from attaining and pursuing their goals. To further buttress this point, Ajayi (2014) acknowledged that conflict is inevitable wherever resources are unequally distributed among competitors and that inequality is reflected in cultural and political relationships between groups.

The Global Coalition for Conflict Transformation (2010) added that conflict is not solely an inherently negative, destructive occurrence but rather a potentially positive

and productive force for change if harnessed constructively. Conflict is not an isolated event that can be resolved or managed but is an integral part of society's ongoing evolution and development. This view tallies with that of Ayayi (2013), who noted that the regularity of conflict has become one of the distinct characteristics of the continent.

The Kruger (2013) revealed that conflicts significantly vary in dimension, progress, and the groups involved. As conflict was observed by Sen (2017) in his standard of living research, some conflicts arise between the same resource user group, such as between one farming community and another, while others occur between different user groups, such as between herders and farmers or between foresters and farmers. Mulin (1996) notes that conflicts in any social system (society) result from differences in perception, limited resources, role conflicts, inequitable treatment, violations of territory, etc.

2.1.2 Communal conflict

According to Gurr (2000), communal conflict is a conflict between non-state groups organised around a shared identity, aiming to gain control over a disputed resource like land or local political power. This type of collective violence is more symmetric than civil wars, as no actor is empowered with the authority of a government or the national army. The groups are not formally organised rebel groups with standing capacities for violence but only occasionally organise to engage in conflict.

Ilvento (2005) highlights the significance of place, interaction, and subsistence in understanding communal conflict. People inhabit a geographic area and work together, creating opportunities for interaction and conflict. Communal conflicts arise from the production and consumption of goods, socialisation, control, and participation (Warren, 1978). They are products of social relations and are directed at territory by one party due to differences over economic issues, power, authority, cultural values, and beliefs (Robinson, 2019). Communal conflict occurs within a geographical area and is influenced by people's interaction, pluralism, and divergences.

Communal conflicts involve groups of individuals who are defined by their collective involvement and are resistant to any actions that threaten or undermine their identity (Oji, Eme, and Nwoba, 2014). Albert (2001) also noted that these conflicts often arise from misunderstandings, where one group views themselves as the rightful owners of land while the other group is seen as 'strangers' or visitors. The 'strangers' often come with their culture and tradition, making them inconvenient to the real land owners. Oboh and Hyande (2006) argue that communal conflicts involve disagreements or violence over issues like land ownership, religious and political differences, leading to loss of life

and property destruction. Eme and Nwoba (2015) further elaborate on communal conflict as a state of incompatibility arising from shared or used property by a group in a society.

Community conflicts, defined by Tadjoeeddin (2002) as violence between different communal groups. These, according to Varshney (2002), are based on religion, tribes, sects, race, and other factors and are referred to as ethnic conflicts. These conflicts can range from Muslim-Christian conflicts in Northern Nigeria to Black and White conflicts in the United States and apartheid South Africa, anti-Chinese riots in Indonesia, the Tiv-Jukun crisis in Nigeria, and Shia-Sunni troubles in Pakistan.

Otite (2006) argues that communal conflicts in minority areas in the South and Middle Belt are primarily caused by domination and oppression, frustration, aggression-displacement, divide-and-rule policies, and diversionary scapegoat techniques. Inequalities in power, wealth, and status distribution, along with domination and oppression by larger groups, have frustrated minority groups, who often fight among themselves rather than unite against oppressors. The breakdown of social control, such as family, education, law, religion, and the political system, has increased ethnic and communal conflicts. The inability to make ends meet in many homes leads to immorality, broken homes, divorces, and drunkenness, leading to street fights.

2.1.3 Educational development

Adebayo (1977) sees education as the total process of human training through which knowledge is imparted, facilitated, and developed. Education is therefore a step to cater for the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor development of an individual. Worsely (1975) defines education as knowledge, as a systematic cultivation of the mind and other natural powers through the acquisition of knowledge and skill through training and instruction. Gofwen (2004) views education as the imparting of knowledge through instruction to effect discipline and maturity of the mind. Hans (1978) on defines education as a science when he asserts that:

Education, as other sciences, is based on facts and observations, which should be ranged in analytical tables easily compared in order to deduce principles and definite rules. Education should become a positive science instead of being ruled by narrow and limited opinions, by whims and arbitrary decisions of administrators, to be turned away from the direct line which it should follow, either by prejudice of a blind routine or by the spirit of some system and innovation.

Educational development is a purposeful activity aimed at enhancing and maintaining the standard of education in society. It involves upgrading educational infrastructure and enhancing the intellectual capacity of tutors (Hoad, 1993). The term has been explored by various theorists, with some viewing it as a process occurring during schooling, teaching, and learning (Peters 2009), while others view it as the mental states and dispositions of educated individuals resulting from socio-development goal intervention by the government. The term may also refer to the academic field studying teaching and learning methods, processes, and social institutions (Giuseffi 2019). Understanding the term is crucial for identifying educational phenomena, measuring success, and improving practices. Educational development occurs within a complex institutional framework, including new class blocks, laboratories, studios, and standard upgrades.

2.1.4 Agricultural development

Agriculture encompasses crop and livestock production, aquaculture, fisheries, and forestry for food and non-food products (Lowder, Sarah K.; Sánchez, Marco V.; Bertini, Raffaele, 2021). Agriculture was the key development in the rise of sedentary human civilization, whereby the farming of domesticated species created food surpluses that enabled people to live in cities. While humans started gathering grains at least 105,000 years ago, nascent farmers only began planting them around 11,500 years ago. Sheep, goats, pigs, and cattle were domesticated around 10,000 years ago. Plants were independently cultivated in at least 11 regions of the world. In the 20th century, industrial agriculture based on large-scale monocultures came to dominate agricultural output.

The major agricultural products can be broadly grouped into foods, fibers, fuels, and raw materials (such as rubber). Food classes include cereals (grains), vegetables, fruits, cooking oils, meat, milk, eggs, and fungi. Global agricultural production amounts to approximately 11 billion tonnes of food, 32 million tonnes of natural fibres and 4 billion m³ of wood. However, about 14% of the world's food is lost from production before reaching the retail level (Chantrell and Glynnis, 2002). Modern agronomy, plant breeding, agrochemicals such as pesticides and fertilisers, and technological developments have sharply increased crop yields but also contributed to ecological and environmental damage. Selective breeding and modern practices in animal husbandry have similarly increased the output of meat but have also raised concerns about animal welfare and environmental damage. Environmental issues include contributions to

climate change, depletion of aquifers, deforestation, antibiotic resistance, and other agricultural pollution. Agriculture is both a cause of and sensitive to environmental degradation, such as biodiversity loss, desertification, soil degradation, and climate change, all of which can cause decreases in crop yield. Genetically modified organisms are widely used, although some countries ban them.

Agricultural development refers to the growth of agricultural land, particularly in the 20th and 21st centuries, driven by the global increase in food and energy requirements due to population growth (Clutton-Brock and Juliet, 1999). They added that with an estimated 10 to 11 billion humans on Earth by the end of this century, non-agrarian ecosystems will be adversely affected, including habitat loss, land degradation, and overexploitation. The intensified food and biofuel production will primarily affect tropical regions. Modern agriculture relies on intensive methods, leading to a significant loss of biodiversity. Agricultural development is also the main driver of deforestation and forest fragmentation, with large-scale commercial agriculture accounting for 40% of tropical deforestation between 2000 and 2010. The need for sustainable practices is urgent due to the massive ecological effects and the proliferation of crops, poultry, goatry, piggery, and palm oil production areas. Land-grabbing activities are often a consequence of the struggle for agricultural land in growing economies.

2.1.5 Socio-economic development

Sandole & Hugo (2003) define socio-economic development as the process of social and economic growth in a society, measured by indicators like GDP, life expectancy, literacy, and employment levels. Friedman (2001) also emphasises the importance of working with households to increase their social power through building social networks, improving knowledge and skills, accessing financial resources, democracy, economic growth, gender equality, and sustainability. Understanding these concepts separately can provide a better understanding of socio-economic development.

According to Johnson, Justin Andrew; Baldos, Uris Lantz; Corong, Erwin; Hertel, Thomas; Polasky, Stephen; Cervigni, Raffaello; Roxburgh, Toby; Ruta, Giovanni; Salemi, Colette; and Thakrar, Sumil (2023), socio-economic development is an organising principle that aims to meet human development goals while also enabling natural systems to provide necessary natural resources and ecosystem services to humans. The desired result is a society where living conditions and resources meet human needs without undermining the planetary integrity and stability of the natural system. Socio-economic development tries to find a balance between economic development, environmental protection, and social well-being. The Brundtland Report

in 1987 defined socio-economic development as "development that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (Mensahand Justice, 2019). The concept of socio-economic development nowadays has a focus on economic development, social development, and environmental protection for future generations.

In 2015, the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) adopted the Socio-economic Development Goals (2015–2030) and explained how the goals are integrated to achieve sustainable development at the global level. The UNGA's 17 goals address global challenges, including poverty, inequality, climate change, environmental degradation, peace, and justice. Socio-economic development is interlinked with the normative concept of sustainability. UNESCO formulated a distinction between the two concepts as follows: "Sustainability is often thought of as a long-term goal (i.e., a more sustainable world), while sustainable development refers to the many processes and pathways to achieve it. The concept of sustainable development has been criticized in various ways. While some see it as paradoxical (or as an oxymoron) and regard development as inherently unsustainable, others are disappointed in the lack of progress that has been achieved so far (Tilman, David; Knops, Johannes; Wedin, David; Reich, Peter; Ritchie, Mark; Siemann, Evan, 1997).

2.1.7 Communal conflicts and educational development

A study by Farah, Limboro, and Kariuki (2021) examined the impact of inter-clan conflicts on secondary schools in Mandera County, Kenya. The research, based on Karl Max's social conflict theory, found that frequent conflicts affected school attendance, infrastructure, and the learning environment. The study also revealed low attendance rates, psychological effects on learners, and a lack of supportive learning environments. Academic performance suffered due to teacher shortages, high absenteeism, inadequate infrastructure, and trauma from conflict. The findings could inform the Ministry of Education and educational stakeholders on how to improve academic performance in conflict-affected areas. The study's findings could inform efforts to improve educational outcomes in conflict-affected areas.

GCPEA (2018) describes perennial communal conflict as a global phenomenon reported in almost every part of the world, which is a major impediment to the realisation of Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) Number 4 of ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all, as more than half of the world's school-going children are estimated to live in conflict-affected fragile states.

WB (2011) opines that conflicts have significant impacts on schooling, leading to the deaths and displacement of both learners and teachers. For instance, the Rwandan Genocide of 1994 resulted in over two-thirds of primary school teachers being killed or displaced, resulting in a shortage of teachers. UNESCO (2013) also reports that conflicts can cause destruction and damage to schools and educational infrastructure. In Bosnia and Herzegovina, 56% of schools required reconstruction and rehabilitation, while in Mozambique, 60% were destroyed or closed due to civil conflict. Conflicts can also prevent school openings, increase absenteeism, and threaten students and teachers' security, resulting in poor syllabus coverage and academic performance.

According to Education for Global Development report (2017), learners in conflict-affected areas face increased exposure to violence, poverty, and neglect, affecting their well-being and access to education. The report also shows that one in six children in Latin America and southern and eastern Africa fails to acquire basic numeracy skills due to conflicts. In countries like Burundi, Congo, Mozambique, Nicaragua, and Senegal, at least one out of every three children does not reach the fourth grade. Despite the 130 million children reported in primary school attendance, 250 million lack basic reading, writing, and math skills. In low-income countries affected by conflicts, less than 5% of learners at the late primary level score above the minimum proficiency level for reading (World Bank Report, 2018).

According to a study by Chui (2016), conflicts reduce the chances of learners passing an exam, which is a very negative predictor of learning in school. This is because, as established by her study, conflict wastes time, depriving the students of engagement in meaningful activities of learning in school and therefore affecting performance both at the individual and school level. Further, Chui argued that conflicts, both at the physical, social, psychological, and emotional levels, cause trauma and distress to students, which has long-term implications for their health and an overall impact on learners' academic achievement in school.

Kasnsuri, Zubir, and Hormias (2012) concluded in their study that conflict can disrupt the learning process by interrupting the learning environment. The quality of learning environments has long-term effects on national examinations and the effectiveness of learning in schools. For instance, in Iraq, conflicts forced over 2.67 million Iraqis to flee their homes and seek refuge in schools, making learning impossible for children. In Pakistan, the conversion of learning centres into residential areas for community members also made the learning environment un conducive, preventing learning from taking place. Therefore, conflict can significantly impact the quality of learning environments.

Conflicts significantly impact both learners and teachers psychologically and socially, with one in five people in conflict-affected areas suffering from depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder, or stress (Lancet 2019). In Burundi, 93% of children interviewed showed signs of troubled behaviour due to the inter-ethnic tension between Hutsi and Tutsi (1992–2005). Katie and Sullivan (2015) posited that when young people undergo traumatic experiences, their sense of understanding becomes shuttered. Consequently, this affects their concentration in school and their academic performance.

A study jointly conducted by UNESCO's Global Education Monitoring Report and the UNHCR and presented at the World Humanitarian Summit (2016) found that learners affected by conflict are five times more likely to be out of school than others. The report revealed how learners in conflict areas were missing a significant and valuable amount of time staying out of class, amounting to months and years, thereby hindering the learning process. The study is not specific to a given region and therefore may not be reflective of the scenario in Ika Local Government Area, in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, further prompting the present study.

Learners' absenteeism from class is high in Mandera County, according to research carried out by the KNEC dubbed "Quality of Education-Status of Learning Outcomes in Schools" conducted between 2013 and 2017, where Mandera County leads by 93% of learners absent from class in Lower Primary. Learners' absenteeism from class leads to poor performance in the national examination. The Ministry of Education report of 2018 concurred with the finding of the KNEC and found out that out of 850,000 children out of school in Kenya, Mandera County leads with 127,000 children out of school, representing 15% of the overall figure nationally, citing constant inter-clan fighting as a factor in child absenteeism from school. The county experienced mass transfers of teachers as a result of the constant terror attacks, increasing the teacher-learner ratio to 1:100, forcing learners to drop some subjects, and thus calling for authorities to recruit untrained and unqualified teachers.

Although the county government of Mandera recruited untrained teachers to replace those who left, according to Winthrop and Kirk (2008), the absence of qualified teachers may lead to difficulties and challenges in correctly implementing the curriculum and solving the issues and problems that conflict can bring into the classroom. Under-qualified and untrained teachers will provide low-quality educational outcomes, as studies by Hunt (2008) and Lewin (2011) have indicated a link between these factors and low academic performance in schools.

According to a study by UNICEF (2014) on Education and Resilience in Kenya's Arid and Semi-Arid Lands, it was discovered that only 5% of children in

primary schools pass their K.C.S.E. examination due to inter-clan fighting over natural resources. The unsafe environment of schools in these areas was also highlighted, with residents of Wajir County and Eldas camped in schools as refuge centres due to conflicts (Salad 2015). Abass (2014) reported that inter-clan conflicts between Garees and Degodia prevented learners from accessing their schools due to attacks, leading to classes ending anytime conflicts began. Teachers reported constant fear and tension in rural areas, leading to nighttime classes and preps being called off. However, the studies were conducted at the primary level, and therefore the present study looked at all the school levels in Ika Local Government Areas in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Conflict, according to UNICEF (2011), increases the risks of sexual and gender-based violence against girls within school environments, such as rape, committed by armed men. In many countries affected by armed conflicts, according to Save the Children (2015), this risk becomes an obstacle for female participation in education, while the absence of female teachers can be another barrier to girls' attendance in schools. Further, girls and female teachers who are exposed to sexual assault as a result of armed conflicts, including those who become pregnant out of rape, are often prevented from attending school because of stigma (UNICEF, 2010). This hinders girls effective participation in the learning process. Conflict affects the lives of children such that, even if they are not killed, they are abducted, raped, or left with emotional scars and psychological trauma from direct exposure to violence or the loss of loved ones (Nathan, 2010). According to UNICEF (2007), 80% of the wars fought in Africa and Asia have left more than 27 million children and youth without access to formal education. A study by the World Bank (2016) on breaking the conflict trap says that conflict constitutes a major obstacle to the achievement of SDG Goal 4 of ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all, as learners in conflict areas lack basic reading, writing, and math skills, resulting in poor learning achievement.

Smith & Vaux (2003) posit that children affected by conflict have special needs since they live in a climate of fear and instability that is not conducive to learning. This is because of the direct experience of persecution or massacre of their family or community members; thus, they are physically and psychologically damaged. They further argued that children affected by conflicts have their attention span reduced, become emotionally demanding, have difficulties concentrating in class, learn concepts, and are overanxious, irritable, and fearful in school. Bishnu (2005) agrees that children who have been affected by conflict are deeply traumatised and develop a strong sense of revenge, hence showing signs of troubled behaviour. Thus, the psychological effects of

conflicts on learners might have a bearing on their academic performance.

2.1.8 Communal conflicts and Agricultural development

Sambe, Avanger, and Alakali (2013) conducted a study on communal conflicts and food security in Africa. The paper adopted the Marxist theory, which stresses group interest and competition for resources as the main causes of communal violence in society. The paper argues that communal conflicts affect food security through limiting people's access to food, the destruction of infrastructure for food production, cutting access to food supplies, and the physical destruction and plundering of crops, livestock, and food reserves. Other impacts include the displacement of labour and the use of food as a weapon of war. Messer and Cohen (2004) opined that in Africa, which has most of its population residing in rural areas, communal conflicts have serious implications for access to and availability of food since agriculture is the main preoccupation of the rural population. The production of crops and the rearing of livestock are the main economic activities of the people. Therefore, communal conflicts have serious implications for the food system. Often, warring communities or parties tactically resort to manipulation over access to food and livestock. Thus, food insecurity has become an effect of communal conflict.

According to the Food and Agricultural Organisation (2004), communal conflict in Africa has cost over \$120 billion in agricultural production in the last third phase of the 21st century, affecting the country's economic wellbeing. These conflicts limit food production and access, leading to chronic food insecurity in sub-Saharan Africa. The Food Research Policy Institute (2004) states that most conflict zones and post-conflict zones in Africa are home to a significant number of food-insecure people. Since 2000, rising food prices have contributed to the increase in food insecurity, from 857 million to 102 billion in 2009 (Food and Organisation-National Programme for Food Security). The organisation suggests that the rising food prices may be linked to persistent communal conflict and violence in developing countries, particularly in Nigeria.

Grada (2007) confirms that communal conflict has been the dominant cause of famine in sub-Saharan African countries hit by crises such as Nigeria, Somalia, Ethiopia, and Mozambique. The United Nations (1993) argues that the ability to produce, trade, and access food is often directly and indirectly affected as a result of violence. Messer Cohen and Marchione (2002) also affirmed that communal conflict crowds out normal economic activities such as food production, thereby subjecting people in such zones to a high risk of food insecurity. The World Food Programme (2004) has further identified the effect of communal conflict on food security. According

to the World Food Programme (2004), communal conflict destroys land, water, and social resources for food production, and thirty million people in more than 60 countries are displaced or have their livelihoods destroyed by conflict every year.

Mohammed (2016) asserts that in Nigeria, which has most of its population residing in rural areas, communal crises have serious effects on access to and availability of food since agriculture is the main preoccupation of the rural population. He further opines that the production of crops and the rearing of livestock are the main economic activities of the people. In recent times, the issue of communal crisis and instability between farmers and nomadic herdsmen across the regions of Nigeria has become a major focus of the Nigerian government, international organisations, and national or indigenous development organisations.

Not only has the communal crisis limited the production of food, but it has also had the propensity to deny people access to food and the availability of food supplies. According to the Food Research Policy Institute (2004), most crisis and post-crisis zones in sub-Saharan Africa are home to substantial numbers of food-insecure people. In most cases, the population in need of food only accounts for a small percentage of the total number of food-insecure people. Sambe, Avanger, and Alakali (2013) confirm that communal crises have been the dominant cause of famine in sub-Saharan African countries hit by crises such as Nigeria, Somalia, Ethiopia, and Mozambique. They argue that the ability to produce, trade, and access food is often directly and indirectly affected as a result of violence.

2.2 Theoretical framework

This research is anchored on social conflict theory and frustration aggression theory.

2.2.1. Social conflict theory

Social conflict theory was derived from the ideas of Karl Marx (1818–1883) and popularised by Edwin Azar in 1990. It explains evolving conflict in communities. It refers to ongoing and seemingly irresolvable conflicts between ethnic groups and communities. Azar emphasizes that these conflicts are rooted in underdevelopment, structural deprivation, economic and psychological issues, and communal or identity cleavages. The theory highlights the interlocking bond between these factors, making them a significant factor in understanding and resolving conflicts.

His theory revealed that many factors account for its emergence and prolonged nature; the factors are economic, political, institutional, cultural, geographical,

psychological, and others. Therefore, conflict occurs when a specific group struggles with others or is deprived of their rights based on communal identity. He argued that it is at this stage of actual physical and economic deprivation that structural victimisation bursts into hostile and violent actions (Azar, 1990).

The theory of communal content and deprivation of human needs explains the reasons for communal conflicts in communities and individuals. Community content refers to the creation of identity, interest, and security of rights and territory, while deprivation of human needs and rights emphasises the reasons for underdevelopment. Azar (1990) argued that deprivation can lead to aggression and may involve resource denial, lack of development, social accessibility for minority groups, or recognition of communal existence. This theory is relevant in understanding the needs and crucial factors responsible for the communal crisis and development challenges in Ika community of Akwa Ibom State. Social conflict occurs when people feel they are denied their rights, such as being part of the community, leadership struggle, domination, and marginalization. The outcome is usually pessimistic, leading to institutionalisation of underdevelopment through destruction of physical and social infrastructure, closure of schools, and farming activities, leading to hardship in the livelihood of the communities involved.

2.2.2 Frustration-Aggression Theory

The proponents of frustration aggression theory are John Dollard, Leonard Bukowitz, and Aubrey Bates (1962). This theory assumes that conflict leading to criminality stems from the inability to fulfil societal needs. This theory suggests that aggression is not a natural reaction but rather a result of frustration when an individual's legitimate desires are denied, either directly or indirectly, due to societal structures. This disappointment can lead to violent conflict, such as killing, maiming, vandalism, and the burning of valuable assets.

Communal conflict among communities, which can lead to socio-economic consequences, is often triggered by unfulfilled needs such as farmlands, water, economic trees, chieftaincy, and political positions. When these needs are denied, frustration can lead to violent conflict, such as killing, maiming, vandalism, and the burning of assets. The theory, therefore, suggests that when frustration becomes widespread, it is crucial to understand the expectations of these groups and find ways to negotiate. Failure to do so can lead to communal conflict, with obvious socio-economic consequences.

Having examined the two theories in explaining and guiding this study, the researcher found social conflict theory more explicitly appropriate to be adopted

because it explains communal conflicts in Ika communities more than frustration theory. Also, relating the theory to Ika, we can say that the area under study is characterised by incessant communal crises over chieftaincy, political leadership positions, and other related resources due to diverse interests among the different clans in the communities, resulting in the loss of lives and properties.

2.3 Empirical Studies

Gbatse, Korinjoh, Shaakaa, and Nungwa (2022) conducted a study on the effects of communal crises on food availability and accessibility in Tivland, Benue State, Nigeria. Conflict theory was employed as a theoretical framework. Data was collected among 380 respondents drawn across Gunia, Gwer West, Tarka, and Vandeikya, Ukum, and Logo LGAs local government areas with a questionnaire and an in-depth interview using cluster and simple random sampling techniques. The test of hypotheses showed that communal crises affect food availability (x2) by 12.275 at 2 (df) and a P-value of .000. The P-value of .000 is less than the critical value of 0.05. Linear regression analysis showed that $B = .412$, $b = 0.229$, $P \text{ value} = 0.00$ i.e. <0.05 values, meaning that communal crises affect food security. Based on the above, the study recommended peace talks between communities and traditional leaders of the warring communities, proper demarcation of the land, and punishing defaulters accordingly.

Adzenga, Umar, Olaleye, Ajayi, and Onyenkazi (2019) conducted a study on farmers' perceived effects of communal conflicts on the delivery of agricultural extension services in north-central Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to obtain a sample size of 391 farmers. Information was elicited using a questionnaire, interview schedule, and focus group discussion and analysed using frequencies, percentages, mean, Likert-type rating scale, and ordered logit regression analysis. The major findings show that the majority of the respondents in the study area perceived communal conflicts to have high effects on the accessibility of extension services. The study recommended that the government should adopt policies that tackle the causes and occurrence of communal conflicts in communities in the country so as to reduce the effects.

Alibi and Famakinwa (2017) investigated the impact of community conflict on rural economic activity in Osun State, Nigeria. The study accessed data through random sampling methods and oral interviews with ninety community members and conducted analysis with descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. Their findings proved that boundary disputes, political tussles among community patricians, chieftaincy disputes, competition among community members over unlimited resources, and issues

related to the payment of tributes. However, it was concluded that loss of properties, reduction in income, and loss of employment, among others, are the consequences.

Okuntade (2017) studied the causes and effects of conflicts in the Nigerian construction industry, identifying 10 key factors and five major severe effects. The determinants of conflicts included win-lose scenarios, failing to share credit, questioning motives, disgruntled clients, diverse perspectives, arrogance, assumption, competitive personality, and feeling judged. However, the five strong effects of conflict included damaged psychological wellbeing, complaints and blaming, dissatisfaction, stress, insubordination, withdrawal, and miscommunication. Bernard and Ashimi (2014) examined the causes, impacts, and remedies of organisational conflict due to competition for supremacy, leadership style, and scarcity of common resources. They concluded that conflict can sometimes produce positive results if it is well managed. They recommended early recognition, attention to conflicting parties, and negotiation between parties involved in conflict resolution, while never using intimidation to resolve conflicting parties. Conflict management approaches should be predictable, deliberate, and external to reduce or avert conflicts.

Deekor and Urho's (2021) study on the influence of communal crises on community development in Udu and Okpe local government areas of Delta State used a descriptive survey design with a sample size of 400 people, representing 20% of the total population. The self-structured questionnaire that was validated using a test-retest method and Pearson Product Moment Correlation for reliability was used for data collection. The study found that social, political, and economic impacts are among the causes of communal crises in society. The researchers recommend that the government, community leaders, and multinational companies organise enlightenment campaigns on the social effects of communal crises and engage youths through empowerment or employment to reduce the rate of communal crises.

Deekor and Kpurunee's study on communal conflicts among the Ogoni people of Rivers State, Nigeria, found that these conflicts negatively impacted healthcare delivery programmes and oil companies' corporate social responsibility for host communities, the Hydrocarbon Pollution Remediation Project (HYPREP). The study used a descriptive survey with 396 respondents, including paramount rulers, chairmen of community development committees, and youth leaders from 132 communities. The results showed that communal conflicts negatively influenced healthcare delivery programmes and hindered community development. The study recommended strict adherence to the 1978 land use decree and the 1990 Act to curtail communal land-related conflicts. It also recommended the development of independent community security systems, focusing on training people to prevent, resolve, and manage conflicts at the communal level. In cases where conflicts are unavoidable, extra care should be taken to

ensure the protection of health workers, farmers, and other essential workers. The study further recommends that where conflicts occur as a result of chieftaincy affairs, such communities should adopt and make the chieftaincy stool of the monarch hereditary to curb conflicts.

Oladimeji, Ayuba, and Ayodele (2019) conducted a study on the effects of communal clashes on socio-economic development: a study of Erin-Ile and Offa, Kwara State, Nigeria. The study employed a convergent parallel design with a structured questionnaire as the main research instrument. The questionnaire was administered to 1,102 respondents purposively selected from the total population of 129,731 people residing in Erin-Ile and Offa. The study found that many lives and property had been lost to these communal clashes between these two towns, with adverse effects on their socio-economic development. This study, among other recommendations, called for the government's takeover of the disputed area between these two to prevent further conflicts between them in the future.

Zhirin, Dauda, and Zailani (2022) examined the impact of communal conflict on agricultural productivity and resolution strategies among farming communities in Benue and Nasarawa States. The research involved 240 participants, including 100 farmers, 100 herdsmen, and 40 traditional rulers. The results showed that communal conflict negatively impacts farming communities, leading to low agricultural production, famine, decreased family income, and a decrease in children's education. The study also highlighted the need for peaceful coexistence among farming communities and a low food supply in the market square. The researchers recommend that traditional rulers, state and federal governments, and the international community work together to educate and enlighten farmers and herdsmen on the importance of co-existing peacefully for sustainable agricultural development.

The literature reviewed only outlined the effects of communal conflicts emanating from politics to ethnic aspects on educational and agricultural development in other local governments. No study has been done so far in Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State on how communal conflicts affect social and economic development in the area. A gap therefore exists in the need to find out and establish the effects of communal conflicts on the socio-economic development in Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Research Methodology

This study adopted an ex-post facto design because of the widespread variables that needed to be captured. The population of the study consists of all 10 political wards in Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, with an emphasis on the warring communities. The actual population as of the time of the study was 102,704 (projected population, 2023) from which 400 respondents were sampled using Taro Yamane's

formula.

The data for this study was both primary and secondary. While the secondary data were gathered from journals, articles, gazette materials, the internet, and newspapers, the primary data came from the researcher-created instrument (a questionnaire) titled "Communal conflict and socio-economic consequences" (QCCSEC). It was face-validated by experts in measurement and evaluation in the faculty of education and the research supervisor. The instrument had a Cronbach reliability coefficient range of 0.78 to 0.84, which indicates a high degree of internal consistency. The analysis of data and the test of the study's formulated hypotheses were done with the Pearson product moment correlation analysis at 0.05 level of significance by using the Statistical Packages for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and Microsoft Excel.

Data Presentation, Analyses and Interpretation of Data

Table 4.2: Frequencies of Responses of respondents, mean, Standard deviations and decision from the survey questionnaire

S/ N	ITEMS	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	N	SD	Decisi on	
1	Communities are not in terms with one another	18 0	13 3	20	12	34 5	3.1625	0.712	
2	Some past conflicts are reignited for continuity	14 0	98	62	45	34 5	2.975	0.832	
3	Communities are so prone to engaging in fight at any slight misunderstanding	98	12 0	70	57	34 5	2.225	1.12	
4	Children inherit their parents' enemies based on past conflicts	67	11 3	87	78	34 5	3.31	1.432	
5	People with political portfolios treats other community citizens unfairly based on conflicts	45	57	11 1	13 2	34 5	1.945	0.45	
Communal Conflicts							2.7235	0.909 2	Agree

Obot, Abasiyanga-owo John; Prof. Enefiok Ibok & Dr. Sunday Ibanga

educational development	1	Teachers and pupils/students go to school from Monday to Friday every week till the end of the term	120	65	76	84	345	1.983	0.87
	2	pupils/students love academic environment	90	68	120	67	345	2.54	0.54
	3	Academic activities cannot be affected by any communal conflict	19	45	125	156	345	2.66	1.04
	4	There is always good performance of pupils/students in class	105	134	54	52	345	2.64	0.92
	5	Parents encourage their wards to go to school and on time	130	87	63	65	345	3.1475	1.21
							2.5941	0.9160	Agree
Farming Activities	1	Farming is done by almost all households	168	135	24	18	345	2.3651	0.94
	2	Farming is an occupation to many	150	134	36	25	345	2.503	0.678
	3	Farming activities cannot be disrupted by any communal conflicts	25	43	125	152	345	2.8075	1.23
	4	Farming is a crucial activity on Saturdays of every week	165	156	14	10	345	3.3925	1.23
	5	People prefer farming to going to market each time the market day falls on Saturday	74	85	88	98	345	2.34	1.05

For a 4-point Likert scale, the control mean is given below:

Control Mean

$$= \frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.5$$

Decision

Obot, Abasiyanga-owo John; Prof. Enefiok Ibok & Dr. Sunday Ibanga

Agree if item mean is greater than or equal to 2.5, but disagree if it is less. From the result in the table above, Communal conflicts has a mean of 2.7235; educational development has 2.5941; agricultural development has 2.6812. Since all their means are above the control mean, it can be concluded that they have a relationship with Communal conflicts.

4.2 The result showing the independent significance of the regression

Research Question one: How do communal conflicts affect educational development in Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State?

Hypothesis one: There is no significant relationship between communal conflicts and educational development in Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4.3: Regression of Educational Development on Communal conflict

Model	R	R-square	p-value	Coefficient
	-0.77	0.5929		
Constant				24.1
Educational development			0.020	-8.21

Source: SPSS Analysis, 2023 Reject H₀ if p-value is < 0.05

From the table above, the correlation coefficient is -0.77 which shows a negative strong relationship between the two variables. The R-square value of 0.5929 shows that educational development has a relationship of about 60% with communal conflicts. The p-value (0.020) shows that the test is significant; hence, the relationship is said to be strong, as explained by the r-square.

The regression equation is given as;

$$AA = 24.1 - 8.21CC$$

The equation above means that every unit increase in the communal conflicts will decrease educational development by 8.21

Research Question Two: To what extent does communal conflict affect agricultural development in Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State?

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between communal conflicts and agricultural development in Ika Local Government Area conflict.

Table 4.4: Regression of Agricultural Development on Communal conflicts

Model	R	R-square	p-value	Coefficient
	-0.86	0.7296		
Constant				17.2
Farming Activities			0.013	-6.05

Source: SPSS Analysis, 2023

Reject H₀ if p-value is < 0.05

From the table above, the correlation coefficient is -0.86 which shows a negative strong relationship between the two variables. The R-square value of 0.7296 shows that agricultural development has a relationship of about 73% with communal conflicts. The p-value (0.013) shows that the test is significant; hence, the relationship is said to be negatively strong, as explained by the r-square.

The regression equation is given as;

$$FA = 17.2 - 6.05 CC$$

The equation above means that every unit increase in the Communal conflicts will decrease Agricultural Development by 6.05

4.3 Discussion of Findings

The main objective of this study was to investigate the influence of communal conflicts on socio-economic development in Ika Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. It does this through two distinct sub-objectives.

The first objective of this study was to investigate how communal conflict affects educational development in Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. It was hypothesised that there is no significant relationship between communal conflicts and educational development in Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. In that test of hypothesis, the independent significance of the regression was ascertained. On the regression of educational development (ED) on communal conflicts, the correlation coefficient was -0.77 which showed a strong and negative relationship between the two variables. The R-square value of 0.5029 showed that educational development had a relationship of about 60% with communal conflicts with a p-value of $0.020 < 0.05$ which

leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis, affirming the result of the R-square value that there is a relationship between the two variables. This result is consistent with UNESCO (2011), which opined that children's education may be truncated by violent conflict through the destruction of schools, directed attacks on teachers, etc. The result is also in line with Nwafor and Koya (2022), who found out that, among others, male and female teachers agreed that chieftaincy disputes, crises over location and natural resources, and farm disputes influence the academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State. Abass (2014) also reported that due to inter-clan conflicts between Garees and Degodia, learners could not access their school because of the attack. From the interview with the indigenous people of Ika local government area during our field survey, it was gathered that classes ended when the conflicts started. Interviews with village heads and teachers showed that because of tension and fear, classes and academic activities were called off due to the fear of attack as class rooms and other school facilities were destroyed and set ablaze in Ika Local Government Areas in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Research and interviews recorded that about twelve (12) secondary schools and about fourteen (14) primary schools were affected (*see Appendix 1*).

On the regression of agricultural development (AD) on communal conflicts, the correlation coefficient was -0.86 which showed a strong and negative relationship between the two variables. The R-square value of 0.7296 showed that agricultural development had a relationship of about 73% with communal conflicts, with a p-value of $0.013 < 0.05$, which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis, affirming the result of the R-square value that there is a relationship between the two variables. This result is consistent with the findings of Adelakun, Adurogbangba, and Akinbile (2015) that incessant resource-based conflicts have continued to undermine the impact of agricultural extension service delivery in Nigeria, resulting in severe effects on the availability of extension services, the adoption of improved technology, and the continued use of adopted technology. Also, Adekunle and Adisa (2010) stated that communal conflicts lead to loss of human lives, farmland, animals, plants, and crops, which have an impact on agricultural production in Nigeria. Simmons (2013) also asserted that production equipment, animals, seed supplies, and food stocks are often casualties of crises and were deliberately destroyed by competing factions. Such destruction hindered agricultural activities from operating in the short term; it also prevented the resumption of productive activities and the recovery of livelihoods in post-crisis periods. From our visit to Ika Local Government Area, it was discovered that during the conflict, farmers were attacked, some were killed, and their houses were

destroyed; also, farm produce and husbandries were destroyed or eroded. These, however, affect agricultural development negatively as farms were abandoned during the communal conflict in Ika Local Government Areas in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria (*See Appendix 2*).

Conclusion and Recommendation

Communal conflicts persist as a major and recurring issue plaguing the socio-economic development of Nigeria, posing a significant challenge to Nigeria's security and development. These conflicts are defined as violent clashes between non-state groups organised around shared cultural, ethnic, or religious identities. The term "communal conflict" encompasses both inter-religious and inter-ethnic conflicts, such as religious violence between Christians and Muslims or tribal clashes. Interestingly, despite ethnic divisions often being at the root of these conflicts, some of the most intense clashes occur within the same ethnic groups, as seen in the conflicts in Ika Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State. These conflicts have severe repercussions on the economy and the development of affected communities.

The economic legacy of such conflicts is a setback for industrialization, educational development, and agricultural development, leading to increased poverty due to the destruction or seizure of farmland, properties, economic assets, and businesses. Recent occurrences of crises over farmland ownership have reignited minor grievances, resulting in the deaths of farmers and potential indicators of future conflict. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that communal conflicts have a strong negative effect on educational development and agricultural development in Ika Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. This means that as communal conflict rises, these two variables reduce in their availability and productivity.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The government should establish a policy that will eradicate and/or control communal conflicts in Ika Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State so as to instill peace in educational activities, hence strengthening education development in the local government area.
2. The government should establish a policy that will eradicate and/or control communal conflicts in Ika Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State so as to instill peace and encouragement in the farming system, thereby strengthening agricultural development for the availability of food.

References

- Abass, I. (2017). No retreat no surrender conflict for survival between the Fulani pastoralist and farmers in northern Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal*. (8): 198-104.
- Adebayo, A. (1977), *Principles and Practice of Public Administration in Nigeria*, Lagos: Spectrum Book Ltd.
- Adelakun, O., Adurogbangba, B. and Akinbile, L. (2015). Socioeconomic effects of farmer-pastoralist conflict on agricultural extension service delivery in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Extension*, 19(2):59-70.
- Albert, I. (2001). *Introduction to third party intervention in community conflict*. Ibadan: John Archers Publishers Ltd.
- Angaye, G. (2003). *Causes and consequences of conflict in Nigeria*. New York: St. martin Press.
- Angaye, G. (2003). *Causes and cures of conflicts in Nigeria*. Macmillan Press.
- Deekor, H. and Urho, P. (2021). Influence of Communal Crises on Community Development in Udu and Okpe Local Government Areas of Delta State. *international Journal of Innovative Development and Policy Studies*, 9(4):40-61.
- Food and Agriculture Organization (FAQ, 2005). *Roles of rural infrastructure in reducing poverty reduction, economy growth and empowerment in Africa Agriculture production year book*, flume, Italy.
- Gbatse, G.; Korinjoh, M.; Shaakaa, K. and Nungwa, M. (2022). The effects of communal crisis of food availability and accessibility in Tivland of Benue State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Reviews*. 12(1):420-429. (ISSN: 2276-8645).
- Gofwen, R. (2004). *Religious Conflicts in Nigeria and Nation Boilding*. Kadiuta: Human Rights Monitor.

Obot, Abasiyanga-owo John; Prof. Enefiok Ibok & Dr. Sunday Ibanga

- Gurr, T. (2000). Peoples versus states; minorities at risk in the new century. Washington, DC: United States Institute of Peace Press.
- Messer, E. and Cohen, M. (2004). Breaking the links between conflict and hunger in Africa. Washington DC: *International Food Policy Research institute*.
- Messer, E., Cohen, M. and Marchiune, T. (2002). Conflict: A cause and effect of hunger. In: *Environmental Change and Security Program Report*, No.7, G. D. Dabelko (ed). Washington D.C. Woodrow: Wilson Centre. pp.1-20.
- Oladimeji, D.; Ayuba, G. and Ayodele, D. (2019). Effect of conflict on the socio-economic development in Nigeria. *International Policy Brief Series Social Science and Law Journal of Policy Review and Development Strategies*, 7(1):
- Otite, O. (2006). *Ethnic pluralism, ethnicity and ethnic conflicts in Nigeria*: Ibadan: Shaneson C. I. Ltd. 2nd edition.
- Pate, U. and Daudu, G. (2009). Indigenous conflict resolution method amongst the Fiber of Adamawa State. <http://www,indegenous/conflictresolution.method>.
- Sambe, N., Avanger, M. and Alakali, T. (2013). Communal violence and food security in Africa. *IOSR journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*.
- Sen, A. (1987). The standard of living (The Tanner Lectures). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Sen, A. (1999), *Development as freedom*, Alfred A. Aknopf. New York. Transparency International (2006), Corruption Perception Index: TI.
- Shut, I. (2017). The challenges of food security in Nigeria. Open Access Library Journal, 4:e4185. Naija-ng.Cdn.amproject.
- Simmons, F. (2013). Harvesting peace: Food security, conflict, and cooperation (Environmental Change & Security Programme Report. 14(3). Washington DC: Woodrow Wilson international Center tot Scholars.

Obot, Abasiyanga-owo John; Prof. Enefiok Ibok & Dr. Sunday Ibanga

UNESCO (2011). *The hidden crisis: Armed conflict and education*. UNESCO: Paris.

United Nations (1993). *World Economic Survey*. New York: United nations.

World Bank (2014). *World development report: Attacking poverty*. NY: Oxford University Press.

Worsely, P. (1975). *Third world*, London: Weidenfeld and Nicolson.

Zhirin, S.; Dauda, A. and Zailani, S. (2022). Impact of Communal Conflict on Agricultural Productivity and Resolution Strategies Among Farming Communities in Benue and Nasarawa States. *Al-Hikmah Journal of Business Education*, 2(2):

Obot, Abasiyanga-owo John; Prof. Enefiok Ibok & Dr. Sunday Ibanga

APPENDIX I

PICTURAL APPENDIX

Communal Conflict effects on Educational Development in Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Devastated structure in Government secondary school Achan Ika caused by damages resulted from communal conflicts in Ika Local Governemnt Area

Abandoned class room block at St. Johns primary school, Ikot Udo, Ika Local Governemnt Area caused by communal conflicts in Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Obot, Abasiyanga-owo John; Prof. Enefiok Ibok & Dr. Sunday Ibanga

Government Primary School, Ikot Uko set ablaze during Ika communal conflicts.

Obot, Abasiyanga-owo John; Prof. Enefiok Ibok & Dr. Sunday Ibanga

APPENDIX II

Communal Conflicts effects on Agricultural Development in Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Abandoned poultry farm in Itung Chan, Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, caused by communal conflicts.

Cassava farm abandoned in Ikot Osukpong, Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, caused by communal conflicts.

Obot, Abasiyanga-owo John; Prof. Enefiok Ibok & Dr. Sunday Ibanga

Abandoned piggery farm in Efen Ibom, Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, caused by communal conflicts.